

E4.2: First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation

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[6GENABLERS-DLT]
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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions**

**Programa de Universalización de
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List of Acronyms

AIO	All-in-one
API	Application Program Interface
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
CLI	Command Line Interface
CRUD	Create-Read-Update-Delete
E2E	End-to-End
HTTP	HyperText Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCM	LifeCycle Management
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
NS	Network Function
PDF	Portable Document Format
PLA	Pricing Logic Algorithm
RAN	Radio Access Network
SC	Smart Contract
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SD	Smart Discovery System
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLA	Service Level Agreement
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtualized Network Function
VSC	Vertical Service Consumer
VSP	Vertical Service Provider
VSV	Vertical Service Vendor

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E4.2 First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). This deliverable provides initial prototype implementation of all platform components related to smart contracts enabled negotiation, together with supporting documentation to describe the specifications and associated operations. This deliverable consists of 1) initial prototype implementation of platform components related to smart contracts enabled negotiation; and 2) document with modules installation and operation guidelines.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Document

Based on the research of deliverable 4.1 [\[1\]](#), this document delves into the development of two essential elements in the Smart Contract (SC) System, the SC Developer Toolkit and the SC State Composer (SCSC). For both components the architecture, implementation, deployment and use are clearly defined.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

Within the project, E4.2 is framed as the second delivery of tasks A4.1 and A4.2, both coming from the result of task A2.3.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The document is structured into multiple chapters that describe the development of the first SC System prototype, focusing on its two central components. Before the chapters, the lists of figures, tables and acronyms are included, along with an executive summary of the deliverable. The references used throughout the chapters are located at the end of the document.

- Chapter 1 (this chapter) focuses on tasks commitment and relationship with the work developed in the rest of the project.
- Chapters 2 and 3 completely cover the development of the prototype of both the SC Developer Toolkit and the SC State Composer. All implementation details are included, as well as documented usage examples, to obtain a complete understanding of the components functioning.
- Chapter 4 includes the final data models used in both Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Consumer (B2C) scenarios.
- Chapter 5 includes an analytical conclusion to obtain a complete vision of the deliverable result.

2 Smart Contract Developer Toolkit

2.1 Scope and Functionalities

As described in [2] the SC Developer Toolkit is a component of the SC System in the form of a Command Line Interface (CLI) tool which is located outside the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It mainly performs tasks related to filling in the input data models as All-In-One (AIO) JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) objects that the rest of the marketplace's components uses. These models are 1) the offering AIO, 2) the order AIO, 3) the SC State AIO.

The way in which the developer creates each AIO model is based on an iteration process, depicted in Figure 2-1. From left to right, it begins by providing a simple description of what the AIO needs to reflect, then the developer will adapt the baseline AIO generated according to their needs, validating each new change. At last, the developer will move on to the SCSC component, described in chapter 3, to make use of the AIO in the Marketplace.

Figure 2-1 - Model creation process using SC Dev Toolkit

The current scope of the prototype is the creation of all planned commands and a set of AIO documents for specific use cases in B2B and B2C scenarios. This will allow the execution of a general test with the rest of the platform components. However, the creation of the AIOs can be applied in many scenarios, making this component a preliminary but essential part of the Marketplace.

2.2 Architecture

The architecture of the component is based on two main parts, a command line interface and a Software Development Kit (SDK) library where the functionality is located. The developer interacts with the CLI by executing commands, which use the logic defined in the SDK to perform the requested functions.

Figure 2-2 - SC Dev Toolkit architecture.

2.2.1 CLI

The CLI is the released output of this component. It has a series of predefined commands, which were introduced in [3]. In the interest of focusing on the developer's needs and the simplicity of the process, some of these commands have been unified into one, while the functionality of others has been moved to the SCSC component. During the development of the prototype, it was decided to separate the functionality into only three core commands, summarized in Table 2-1. Each of them has a specific function, and their definition and use will be explained in the following subsections.

Table 2-1 - SC Dev Toolkit command suite

Command	Description	Example of use
Generate	Creates a baseline AIO document ready to be filled and customized.	A developer wants a VNF offering template to start preparing a service offer.
Attachment	Converts documents and compressed tar.gz files to an attachment valid TM Forum model ready to be included in an AIO.	A developer wants to include a PDF with the license model in the AIO template.
Validate	Validates an AIO document against a reference JSON schema of its type and semantics.	A developer wants to check if their customized AIO is valid to be uploaded to the Marketplace.

2.2.2 SDK

Both, the SC Developer Toolkit and the SCSC components are built on top of an SDK where all the logic and functionality reside. This library is organized as described in the Figure 2-3.

Figure 2-3 - SDK Internal modules.

2.2.2.1 Templates and Validation

This module is dedicated to implementing the template generation and validation logic. It includes the templates that will be generated when the developer requests it and the schemas used in validation.

It is relevant to highlight that both syntactic and semantic validation takes place in the two components of the SC System, the Dev Toolkit when the user requests it and in the SCSC automatically when receiving an AIO document.

2.2.2.2 Digital Content

This module includes the functionality that interacts with the user file system by creating attachment models for the chosen documents. The module is capable of processing documents, for example legal agreements in PDF format, and compressed files in tar.gz format, such as the artifact of a Virtualized Network Function (VNF) or Network Service (NS).

2.2.2.3 Render

This module contains functions that specialize in rendering a PDF file using a template that is based on Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) files. This is the legal prose template. The functions obtain information from different AIO files and automatically generate a rendered PDF, included in the Product Order. Essentially, it analyses the legal prose template to inject the necessary values and return it for a final review before including it in the corresponding model.

2.2.2.4 Integrations

This module is responsible for including integration points with the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and Smart Discovery services to be able to use the related functionality of these systems.

2.2.2.5 AIO LCM

This module stores the logic related to the creation of the SC State, the functionality to process and translate messages received as events over the Data Bus to update the corresponding AIOs that are already stored in the DLT.

2.3 Internal Operational Workflows

Figure 2-4 - Asset Offering Creation using SC Dev Toolkit

As can be seen in Figure 2-4 the user converts all documents, referring to price, licenses, and even the asset artifact itself into attachment models ready to be included in the resulting AIO.

Figure 2-5 - Asset Order Creation using SC Dev Toolkit

Figure 2-5 shows the process of generating an AIO order. During the execution of the Validate command, if the AIO template is syntactically and semantically correct after the developer's modifications, the rendering process of the Legal Prose Template that is included in the associated offer begins.

There is no manual process for creating the SC State AIO model since it is an automatic process which occurs when the instantiation of an order is requested.

2.4 Implementation

2.4.1 Technologies

The technologies used for the development of the SC Developer Toolkit have been chosen keeping in mind the functions that had to be performed and trying to ensure the minimal system requirement needed to use it. The CLI itself can be compiled on different operating systems, including Windows, any Linux distribution, MacOS, any BSD distribution, Illumos, Plan9 and Solaris. It is released as a standalone binary which does not have any system's library dependencies.

2.4.1.1 Go

Go [\[4\]](#), or Golang, is a programming language developed by Google, characterized by its simplicity and efficiency, and used to develop a wide variety of applications, from command line programs to distributed systems or high-scale applications. Some of the main features of Go are the following:

- Open-source project.
- Static typing.
- Compiled language, like C or C++.
- The binaries have the cross-compilation feature natively.
- It supports the object-oriented paradigm, but unlike other languages, it has no inheritance or other statements that indicate that it clearly supports this paradigm.
- It is clearly aimed at taking advantage of multiprocessor systems and network processing.

In the SC Dev Toolkit scenario, it has been used to develop both the main functionality of the SDK and the command suite.

It is also important to mention the Cobra library. This library focuses on creating modern command line interfaces in Go projects, and is used in large projects such as K8s, Hugo and GitHub CLI.

Cobra's high flexibility allows the creation of commands, nested commands, flags, command documentation and it is also POSIX-compliant. In the SC Dev Toolkit, Cobra has been the central part in the development of the CLI using the functionalities of the modules seen in 2.2.1.

2.4.1.2 JSON Schema

The data models implemented in the SC System, aligned with TM Forum [\[5\]](#) are written in JSON markup language. Due to this, the use of JSON schemas [\[6\]](#) in development has been necessary.

JSON Schema is a declarative language for validating the structure, constraints, and data types in JSON documents. It allows to define the expectations of the JSON file. This makes it simpler to exchange data between applications because the data follows a consistent pattern. Using these schemas ends up making JSON models more readable and improves data validation since applications can check the defined criteria.

Specifically, these schemas have been used to define the exact structure that the JSON models of the three existing AIO types (Offer, Order and SC State) should have. This functionality is precisely what is behind the "validate" command seen in 2.2.1. Once the developer has completed their AIO model, that file is compared to its related schema.

2.4.1.3 Scaffold Go Library

Additionally, some tool or language was necessary that would allow the creation of an initial schema for the developer. In this way, the developer could have a first sketch of an AIO model that would be filled later. The option chosen was a scaffold template library that had synergy with Golang, specifically [\[7\]](#). This library allows to define an initial structure of the AIO document based on some parameters provided by the developer. In this way, this first version of the AIO document adapts to those parameters and modifies parts of its code as necessary. This functionality is directly linked to the generate command, which was introduced in 2.2.1.

2.4.1.4 Chromedp Package

The package for Go, Chromedp [\[8\]](#), is a Chrome DevTools client that provides great functionality when performing tasks such as web scraping, unit testing or profiling web pages. This package has no third-party dependencies. In the render module of the SC Dev Toolkit, seen in 2.2.2, it has been used to process the HTML files that will include their information in the Legal Prose Template prior to rendering.

The process of generating AIO templates is complex, and it is necessary to have a global vision of all the related AIOs and how to reach the necessary fields to replace them in the template. For this reason, the Offer AIOs will include a Legal Prose Template predefined by the SC System according to the type of asset being treated.

2.4.2 Interfaces

2.4.2.1 Exposed

The developer interacts with the SC Dev Toolkit through the CLI. The commands defined and exposed to the user are the access points to the functionality it offers, as seen in Figure 2-2.

- **Generate**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli generate -h
Generates an AIO template model for offer/order on the selected folder based on the developer preferences.

Flags:

--type:

    B2B: The template is based on a B2B approach.
    B2C: The template is based on a B2C approach.

--asset:

    VNF: The template follows the VNF asset structure.
    NS: The template follows the VNF asset structure.
    EDGE: The template follows the EDGE asset structure.
    CLOUD: The template follows the CLOUD asset structure.
    RAN: The template follows the RAN asset structure.
    SLICE: The template follows the SLICE asset structure.
    SPECTRUM: The template follows the SPECTRUM asset structure.

--license:

    perpetual: The license model of the template is perpetual (in-full).
    opensource: The license model of the template is open-source (in-full).
    recurring: The license model of the template is recurring (rental).
    service: The license model of the template is as-a-service (rental).

--pricing:

    flat: The pricing model of the template is flat.
    tiered: The pricing model of the template is tiered.
    subscription: The pricing model of the template follows a subscription model.
    payg: The pricing model of the template follows a PAYG (pay-as-you-grow) model.

Usage:
  scsccli generate [OFFER/ORDER] [PATH_TO_DIRECTORY] [flags]
```

Figure 2-6 - Generate command.

The generate command shown in Figure 2-6 allows the developer, indicating the type of AIO document, to obtain a template of that document which contains the necessary placeholders and default values. The template is returned as a local JSON file. It is possible to pass some flags to this command to further customize the developer's preferences from the beginning, such as, for example, to indicate whether the template should be oriented to a VNF or NS among other assets. These possible arguments are explained to the developer using help or in the command extended description.

- **Attachment**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli attachment -h
Generates an attachment model in a JSON file, ready to be included in an offer/order model, using an input PDF or tar.gz.

Usage:
  scsccli attachment [PATH_TO_PDF]
```

Figure 2-7 - Attachment command.

Attachment command, shown in Figure 2-7, is used to fill attachments in AIO models. From the file path, the command returns a representation of the file in JSON, which is ready to be included in the offer or order template created by the developer.

Two variations of the attachment model are needed depending on the file. Some examples such as an agreement's PDF, monitoring scripts, the legal prose template, the license model applied to an offer, and the pricing script for calculating the recurring cost of using the asset, can be directly encoded and embedded in the document with their base64 representation [9]. Other files, such as the artifact of the asset (VNF/NS tar.gz file), are too heavy for this approach and, instead, the digital digest of the file is used to at least have a way of ensuring that said file is not changed after it is onboarded into the Marketplace.

- **Validate**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli validate -h
This command validates a JSON model with an internal schema.json file, based on the type of JSON and the path to it.
Usage:
  scsccli validate [OFFER/ORDER/SCSTATE] [PATH_TO_MODEL.JSON]
```

Figure 2-8 - Validate command.

Figure 2-8 command focuses on the validation of an AIO model by the developer. This validation compares the file selected by the developer with a predefined JSON schema of the specific AIO. Using the path to the file as input, the command returns an error if there is a syntax error, missing required field or incorrect value.

Furthermore, if the command is being executed on an Order AIO template, and is syntactically and semantically correct, a rendering process of the Legal Prose Template of the offer associated with this order is initiated. The SC Dev Toolkit requests this rendering from the SCSC, and when it receives the rendered PDF, it includes it in the AIO Order model and returns the result to the developer.

Additionally, the CLI implements marketplace-specific validations over the AIO to ensure that those files which other systems rely on to perform their functionality, are semantically correct with the rest of the AIO.

2.4.2.2 Consumed

The SC Dev Toolkit only has one interaction with another component, the SCSC. This interaction occurs during the rendering process of the Legal Prose Template of an Offer, to include it in the validation of the Order AIO. The SC Dev Toolkit requests this rendering to an SCSC endpoint, which processes the request, generates the PDF, and returns it. This endpoint is of type internal and is defined as /render. Its complete structure can be seen at the end of annex 7.1.

2.5 Deployment

2.5.1 Installation Procedure

Installing the SC Dev Toolkit is a simple procedure. To do this, simply download the binary from the Git repository of the project. By running the binary, it is possible to use all the functionality of the component.

2.5.2 User Documentation

The user documentation for the SC Dev Toolkit can be found by running the help command, as shown in Figure 2-9. The developer can now see all the possible commands available to them and their explanation, as well as the arguments they can use, if any.

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli --help
CLI utility to assist on the creation of the AIO of a Smart Contract

Usage:
  scsccli [command]

Available Commands:
  attachment  Generates an attachment model in a JSON file using an input file (pdf or tar.gz).
  generate     Generates an AIO template model for an offer/order.
  help        Help about any command
  validate    Validates a JSON offer/order/scstate model.

Flags:
  -h, --help  help for scsccli
```

Figure 2-9 - Help command.

2.5.3 Integration Guidelines

The only necessary integration of the SC Dev Toolkit is with the SCSC, for the reasons explained in 2.4.2.2 about the rendering of the Legal Prose Template.

2.6 Results and Next Steps

The results of using the SC Dev Toolkit have been successful and, as has been verified in 2.2.1 all commands are functional. Furthermore, this component is essential to show functional B2B and B2C scenarios since it is the first step in generating valid AIO documents. These documents are the final output of the SC Dev Toolkit and are detailed in Chapter 4. Furthermore, functional and unit tests have been developed as part of the codebase of this component.

The next steps to improve the component are to establish a link with other teams in the consortium so that the SC Dev Toolkit can address the specific needs of their scenarios if necessary. Another key point is to help in the creation of AIO data models for the rest of the use cases.

The existing functionality and future flexibility will make this component a useful tool in preparing elements ready to be integrated into the decentralized 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

3 Smart Contract State Composer

3.1 Scope and Functionalities

The SCSC is a central component of the SC System, deployed in the same infrastructure as the Marketplace, which allows interaction with the DLT. In addition, it represents the entry point for stakeholders who want to offer their resources and services or consult those provided by others. It also has communication with the Smart Discovery System (SD), which allows a stakeholder to find available offers related to their interests based on an intent.

Finally, it reacts to alarms and events generated in other systems that organize and monitor the deployment of assets. In this way, the SCSC includes them in the corresponding DLT transaction and, if necessary, the availability of an already-integrated asset is modified so that other stakeholders are aware.

Other than the Application Program Interfaces (APIs) exposed to the stakeholders, the focus is threefold:

1. Creation of the SC State when an order is requested to be instantiated.
2. Rendering of the Legal Prose Template into a PDF document aggregating in a human-readable format, the legal binding of the transaction.
3. Perform the necessary LifeCycle Management (LCM) operations over the already-approved offers and orders.

3.2 Architecture

The SCSC is based on a microservices architecture, a Rest API and a set of listeners to obtain events and alerts from the Data Bus. The Rest API focuses on three main things: Create-Read-Update-Delete (CRUD) operations for the required AIO (input data models) [\[10\]](#), CRUD operations for the SC State (output data model) [\[11\]](#), and interactions with the DLT layer. Both the API and the set of listeners (Kafka consumer) are deployed in Kubernetes.

The SCSC has the characteristic of being a stateless element, that is, it does not retain information about the user's previous transactions. Each transaction is executed independently and without relying on the past stored anywhere else other than in the DLT. Due to this, the SCSC does not need to have an associated database, since it behaves as an element that processes requests and returns results in real time.

Figure 3-1 shows a diagram with the architecture of the component and its interaction both with a user through the Swagger UI and with other external elements through its APIs or the Data Bus. In addition, the SDK block presented in 2.2.2 is shown as the SCSC also interacts with some of its modules.

Figure 3-1 - SCSC Architecture

3.2.1 Swagger API

As presented in [\[12\]](#) the SCSC provides a REST API in the form of a web service that can be consumed directly from a browser. This service follows the OpenAPI v2.0 specification, and is organized into four sections to differentiate existing endpoints:

- Supply: Endpoints that allow models to be uploaded to the Marketplace.
- Demand: Endpoints that allow the management, purchase, and request for deployment of existing offers in the Marketplace.
- Deployment: Endpoints that allow a way to consume previously ordered items from the Marketplace by requesting their instantiation.
- Internal: Endpoints that are necessary for the correct functioning of the system and the interactions between the components of the SC System, for example, in the communication between the SC Dev Toolkit and the SCSC when rendering the Legal Prose Template.

This Rest API has been developed entirely in Go language and has been documented for a good understanding of its functionality using Swagger [\[13\]](#).

3.2.2 Listeners

The SCSC has Kafka listeners, which is also an API but event-driven, to receive events and status updates through the Data Bus. These listeners can be seen in Figure 3-2 along with the external elements that send alerts to the Data Bus.

Figure 3-2 - Kafka listeners.

3.3 Internal Operational Workflows

Figure 3-3 - Internal Offer Intent Management

Figure 3-3 shows the interaction of a user who wants to discover new offers available in the Marketplace through an intent based on their preferences.

Figure 3-4 - Internal AIO Document Reception Management.

Figure 3-4 shows how a user sends an AIO document to the SCSC API that automatically validates its syntax and semantics before requesting its inclusion in the corresponding DLT API.

On the other hand, Figure 3-5 shows how the SCSC Kafka Listeners API receives an event and, as a result, a long process of updating that offer/order model and its associated SC State begins. Communication with the DLT APIs is performed by the SCSC API while event reception and updates are performed by the Kafka Listeners API.

Figure 3-5 - Internal Event Management

Finally, Figure 3-6 shows the instantiation process of an order previously acquired by a user. The associated orders, if any, are recovered and an SC State is generated for each one.

Figure 3-6 - Internal Instantiation Request Management

3.4 Implementation

3.4.1 Technologies

Since the entire logic of the SC System is developed in the Go language, already presented in 2.4.1.1, the API and listener microservices for the data bus have also been developed in Go. The way in which these two microservices have been implemented will be explained below.

3.4.1.1 Swagger

APIs allow data and information to be shared between different elements in a system. One of the main problems they face is not having a common design standard or appropriate documentation. This slows down the way some elements interact since the connectivity between them must be taken more into account. One solution is to use an

extended API framework, the best-known being Swagger [\[14\]](#). With Swagger it is easy to create a set of rules and specifications to document the API, so anyone can understand how it works.

Swagger UI uses an existing JSON or YAML document and makes it interactive. With this, it creates a platform to organize the CRUD methods of the API and categorizes the operations. Each method is expandable, and it is possible to view the path parameters.

In any case, Swagger allows us to document our API, but not define its logic. To do this, it is necessary to implement some methods, in this case in Go, to define the actions of each API method.

3.4.1.2 Kafka Listeners

Also developed in Go, a Kafka listener consists of code that allows handling events in real time. The goal is to capture the time value of the event. In the offer and order scenario in a decentralized Marketplace, it is essential to listen to events that apply to already deployed services, since these events modify the behaviour of the services. This microservice is implemented in the SCSC to handle the following events:

- Service Level Agreement (SLA) Violations
- Offering Violation Events
- Availability Notifications
- Deployment Statuses

3.4.2 Interfaces

3.4.2.1 Exposed

The exposed interfaces are organized in the SCSC Swagger documentation. The file associated with this documentation, *swagger.yaml*, is included in the annex at the end of this document. The interfaces are divided into four sections: supply, demand, deployment and internal. The purpose of these sections was presented in 3.2.1.

3.4.2.2 Consumed

The interfaces that the SCSC consumes from other elements are the following:

- Data Bus:
 - o Events specified in 3.4.1.2
- DLT APIs:
 - o SC State API
 - o Order API
 - o Offering API
- Smart Discovery:
 - o Intent-based Discovery API

The relationship between the messages received by the Data Bus and the events that the SCSC expects to generate is found in the Table 3-1. The messages and their nomenclature have been obtained from [15]. These events are included in the "Events" structure in the SC State AIO model.

Table 3-1 - Events and messages

Event	Associated received message	Sender	Purpose
SLA Violation Prediction	alert	Proactive SLA Monitoring	A potential SLA Violation has been predicted by the platform.
SLA Violation	alarm	Proactive SLA Monitoring	Indicates that any of the conditions or rules of the SLA have been breached.
Offering Violation	To be defined	To be defined	Indicates that any of the conditions or rules of the Offering have been breached.
Availability	availability_response	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	Monitoring the availability of the resources of an offer.
Deployment Status	deployment_status	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	Indicates the status of an offer deployment.

The Offering Violation event is not implemented yet, since it is a very characteristic event for advanced use case testing. Its inclusion will come later in the end-to-end (E2E) phase of the project.

3.5 Deployment

3.5.1 Installation Procedure

The deployment of this module is based on the use of Helm Charts. The first step to install the SCSC is to adapt the *values.yaml* file. This file, shown in Figure 3-7, contains information relevant to the deployment of the API such as the IP address and ports. It also indicates which image to use in the installation.

```
image:
  api:
    tag: latest
    image: registry.atosresearch.eu:18467/scsc
    inPort: 8080
    outPort: 30880
    pullPolicy: Always
    sdUrl: 172.27.13.254:32766
  listener:
    tag: latest
    image: registry.atosresearch.eu:18467/scsc
    brokerUrl: 172.27.13.249:31090
    pullPolicy: Always
```

Figure 3-7 - Values.yaml file.

Now, the way to install SCSC is by running a command to install the helm chart, as shown in Figure 3-8.

```
helm install scsc $PATH_TO_CHART
```

Figure 3-8 - SCSC installation command.

\$PATH_TO_CHART is equivalent to the root of the project, and then the command is completed with "cicd/k8s-install/scsc-chart".

The result of the SCSC installation includes the following pods and services:

- 1 pod: Two containers.
 - o Rest API
 - o Listeners
- 1 services: Nodeport to expose the Rest API
- Configmaps and secrets for internal environment variables.

3.5.2 User Documentation

All the information and documentation necessary for a user to use the SCSC is stored in Swagger UI. The exact address depends on the installation but is based in the structure shown in Figure 3-9.

```
cluster_ip:{values.image.api.outPort}/swagger/index.html
```

Figure 3-9 - Swagger.ui path.

3.5.3 Integration Guidelines

As can be seen in Figure 3-10, a log of the Kafka listeners receiving events correctly through the Data Bus is shown. This demonstrates that a correct integration has been established with one of the essential parts of the system.

```

null|@ESKTOP-161000|~/workspace/ariel@github:~/SMART-CONTRACTS/cicd/88-Installs| kubernl logs scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 -c listener $XGGE
11:55:35.992 env_vars.go:16 WRA 001 | Unable to read env file .env, open .env: no such file or directory
11:55:35.993 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 004 | entering loop for consumer group, SCSC
11:55:35.992 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 002 | entering loop for consumer group, SCSC
11:55:35.993 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 003 | entering loop for consumer group, SCSC
11:55:35.993 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 005 | entering loop for consumer group, SCSC
11:55:35.993 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 006 | entering loop for consumer group, SCSC
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 007 | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5173663b-5f6a-46cd-b6aa-925cb871e779 in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 008 | selected as leader for group, SCSC
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 00a | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-47071d26-accb-45a5-8645-9b281952a11d in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 00b | joinGroup succeeded for response, SCSC, generationID=4, memberID=sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-47071d26-accb-45a5-8645-9b281952a11d in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 00c | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-47071d26-accb-45a5-8645-9b281952a11d in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 009 | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-a0f79d7a-d8e3-4525-933d-4a4661591e5 in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 00d | joinGroup succeeded for response, SCSC, generationID=4, memberID=sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-a0f79d7a-d8e3-4525-933d-4a4661591e5 in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 00e | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-a0f79d7a-d8e3-4525-933d-4a4661591e5 in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 010 | joinGroup succeeded for response, SCSC, generationID=4, memberID=sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 011 | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 012 | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5983fc46-41dc-48e7-830e-a62b2c3bb887 in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 013 | joinGroup succeeded for response, SCSC, generationID=4, memberID=sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5983fc46-41dc-48e7-830e-a62b2c3bb887 in generation 4
11:56:05.446 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 014 | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5983fc46-41dc-48e7-830e-a62b2c3bb887 in generation 4
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 015 | using 'range' balancer to assign group, SCSC
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 016 | found member: sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5173663b-5f6a-46cd-b6aa-925cb871e779 [1byte(nil)
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 017 | found member: sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-a0f79d7a-d8e3-4525-933d-4a4661591e5 [1byte(nil)
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 018 | found member: sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5983fc46-41dc-48e7-830e-a62b2c3bb887 [1byte(nil)
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 019 | found member: sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b [1byte(nil)
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 01a | found member: sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-47071d26-accb-45a5-8645-9b281952a11d [1byte(nil)
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 01b | found topic/partition: alarm/0
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 01c | found topic/partition: alert/0
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 01d | found topic/partition: availability_response/0
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 01e | found topic/partition: deployment_status/0
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 01f | assigned member/topic/partitions sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b/availability_response/[0]
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 020 | assigned member/topic/partitions sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b/alert/[0]
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 021 | assigned member/topic/partitions sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b/alarm/[0]
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 022 | assigned member/topic/partitions sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-e276489b-41d0-4599-97bb-cf31bdc836b/deployment_status/[0]
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 023 | joinGroup succeeded for response, SCSC, generationID=4, memberID=sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5173663b-5f6a-46cd-b6aa-925cb871e779
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 024 | joined group SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5173663b-5f6a-46cd-b6aa-925cb871e779 in generation 4
11:56:05.447 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 025 | syncing $ assignments for generation 4 as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-5173663b-5f6a-46cd-b6aa-925cb871e779
11:56:05.458 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 026 | received empty assignments for group, SCSC as member sccslisteners@scsc-74f968668c-dfm14 (github.com/segmentio/kafka-go)-a0f79d7a-d8e3-4525-933d-4a4661591e5 for generation 4
11:56:05.458 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 027 | sync group finished for group, SCSC

```

Figure 3-10 - Kafka integration.

On the other hand, Figure 3-11 shows the successful integration of the SD. It is possible to see how this component returns the list of available offers.

```

Running tool: /usr/local/bin/gln/g test -timeout 30s -run '*TestRealServiceDiscovery$ github.gissic.nyotas.net/GLB-BDS-ETSN-SECURITY/INF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc/pkg/integrations
=== RUN TestRealServiceDiscovery
13:12:02.473 service_discovery_test.go:22 INF 001 | [map[BlueprintName:cloud_cache_nst_id:map[id:60f9b9c99a1abf35bd2ce33] category:[map[referredType:Category href:http://serverLocation/port/catalogManagement/category/13 id:3da0b6f5-a86f-48c-9f93-a29a631ca3] name:Cloud offerings version:2.0]] description:Cloud resource virtual href:cloudResourceID id:466594 isBundle:0 isSellable:0 lifecycleStatus:Active name:virtual node place:[map[city:Athens country:Greece geoip:unitLocation:[map[geoip:[map[id:2ab0cf8b-978b-488b-33a-826a0954d80 e242.6170207565213 y:150.18538629476842 z:]] geometryType:Point name:Company href:http://1372.28.3.126:31800/inf-api/geographicAddressManagement/v4/geographicAddress/830c7248-4eb4-4f08-b01e-86669e947540 id:81c42621-707c-4498-9108-72488883ca locality:Ymlia 3, Athens Greece]] productOfferingPrice:[map[baseType: @schemeLocation:http://serverLocation/port/catalogManagement/schema/ProductOfferingPrice .xml @type:ProductOfferingPrice description:monthly price href:http://serverLocation/port/catalogManagement/productOfferingPrice/161 id:3819 name:Monthly Price map[UNIT:EUR value:1925] priceUsage: recurringChargePeriod:monthly unitOfMeasure: validFor:[map[endDate:2028-09-07T00:00 startDate:2020-09-14T00:00] version:1.0]] productSpecification:[map[baseType: referredType: name:productSpecification relateParty:[map[party:http://serverLocation/port/management/party/610124 id:4802662-6760-4f46-ae08-3975e2723a4e name:operator role:owner validFor:[map[endDate:2021-11-10T00:00 startDate:2021-04-14T00:00]] resourceSpecification:[map[category:cloud compute description:edgesResourceSpec href:http://id:64440a1-4e42-4443-8041-e0112465312c name:cloudResourceSpec resourceSpecCharacteristic:[map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory configurable:false description:The number of cpu cores of the cloud resource, extensible:false id:c49f76f-7c76-4298-8885-875f37c2e6b isUnique:false name:sum of cores resourceSpecCharacteristicValue:[map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory id:Default: false unitOfMeasure:Mhz validFor:[map[endDate:2021-09-14T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:4]] validFor:[map[endDate:2021-09-17T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:numeric version:1.0]] map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory configurable:true description:The core cpu frequency (MHz) of the cloud resource, extensible:false id:862c795a-a722-43a1-8f22-bc90bb6b677 isUnique:false name:coreFrequency resourceSpecCharacteristicValue:[map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory id:Default: false unitOfMeasure:Mhz validFor:[map[endDate:2021-09-17T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:3751]] validFor:[map[endDate:2021-08-19T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:numeric version:1.0]] map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory configurable:true description:The memory size of the cloud resource expressed in MB, extensible:false id:a003786-5d31-46c7-a449-9b6d70ba isUnique:true name:memory resourceSpecCharacteristicValue:[map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory id:Default: true unitOfMeasure:GB validFor:[map[endDate:2021-09-17T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:8]] validFor:[map[endDate:2021-09-17T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:numeric version:1.0]] map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory configurable:true description:The storage size of the cloud resource expressed in GB, extensible:true id:4b70c962-140f-4102-9f0e-2272c4b0f77a isUnique:true name:storage resourceSpecCharacteristicValue:[map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory id:Default: true unitOfMeasure:GB validFor:[map[endDate:2021-08-19T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:1362]] validFor:[map[endDate:2021-08-19T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:numeric version:1.0]] map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory configurable:true description:The network speed of the cloud resource expressed in Mbps, extensible:false id:b0878ca-525f-43b-a4c6-8a6869c6af isUnique:true name:bandwidth resourceSpecCharacteristicValue:[map[baseType:Category @type:ResourceCategory id:Default: true unitOfMeasure:Mbps validFor:[map[endDate:2021-08-19T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:100]] validFor:[map[endDate:2021-08-19T00:00 startDate:2021-05-14T00:00] value:numeric version:1.0]] version:v0.1]] product_id:3ece5f51-aab2-43ae-81ce-e50f8e6c549 resourceCandidate:[map[pref:https://mycsp.com/8080/inf-api/resourceCatalogManagement/v4/resourceCandidate/9338 id:2603823 9-b071-40c8-97c6-cafa2e9557 name:Cloud candidate] resource_id:0810f019-9403-88c7-a554-ar2d30010c serviceCatalogItem:[map[approvalId description:ServiceLevelAgreement href:https://mycsp.com/8080/inf-api/slaManagement/v4/sla/0802 name:business sla relateParty:[map[ref:http:// name:ID9 role:slaProvider validFor:[map[endDate:2028-09-07T00:00 startDate:2020-05-14T00:00]] rule:[map[consequence:extra credit href:https:// name:response_time metric:ht tp://www.provider.com/metrics/response-time operator:gc referenceValue:

```

Figure 3-11 - Smart Discovery integration.

Finally, the last essential point of integration is with the DLT APIs. This communication is still in development process and will soon be completed, showing the integration in document E4.3.

3.6 Results and Next Steps

In the development and implementation of the SCSC prototype, the following results have been achieved:

- Deployment of the component in K8s and exposure of the APIs.

- Alignment with the latest advances of all the elements with which the SCSC communicates, such as other external systems from other partners in the consortium.
- First version of all functional blocks.

Finally, the next steps expected for the SCSC in its following releases are:

- Integrate and test AIO LCM functionalities as part of the listener workflow.
- Test all AIO models in the E2E scope.
- Verification of the registration of an AIO in the DLT and receipt of the associated DID.
- Establish a link with other teams in the consortium so that the component can address the specific needs of their scenarios if necessary.

4 Data Models

This section focuses on updating the information previously presented in documents [\[16\]](#) and [\[1\]](#) about data models. The use case is the same as the one introduced in them, and the status is very advanced so no new modifications should be found in the future.

The use case is divided into two scenarios, one B2B and the other B2C, which will be explained in 4.1 and 4.2, respectively. For simplicity, a VNF and a NS have been chosen directly from the Opensource Mano (OSM) public repository to develop the AIO documents of the use case. This function and network service are focused on the deployment of a Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) service.

4.1 B2B Scenario

The B2B scenario replicates a situation in which a Vertical Service Vendor (VSV) wants to sell a specific simple service on the Marketplace. That service has been converted to a virtualized network function.

The developer wants the service to be acquired through an initial payment and subsequently, depending on its use, a monthly amount that varies. To do this, there are a series of documents which must be prepared, such as the Pricing Logic Algorithm (PLA) scripts, which monitors the use of the service to calculate the amount to pay. Also documents with certain legal content such as the license model or the Legal prose template. These documents are transformed into structures that can be included in the AIO using the SC Dev Toolkit.

It is noteworthy to mention that AIOs contain an initially empty ID field when they are generated in the Dev Toolkit. This field is filled by the DLT with the DID when the AIO is received.

The following sections will show each AIO document related to this scenario. These documents have a DID, simulating that they have already interacted with the DLT, to show their final form.

4.1.1 VNF Offering AIO

In Figure 4-1 a VNF product offering is presented. In this case, VSV has decided to customize its template with the following characteristics:

- **Place:** Barcelona.
- **License Model:** Perpetual. The seller wants the VNF buyer to make an initial payment to purchase the right to have the product. The quantity is defined in the *price* structure, with an amount of 120 euros.
- **Recurring Price:** The seller wants to generate benefits for the use of the VNF, so he establishes an amount of 50 euros per month for its use.
- **VNF Artifact:** The seller includes its own VNF artifact as an attachment in the offer.
- **vCPU, Memory and Storage requirements:** The seller defines the number of vCPU cores, RAM and storage as requirements of the machine where the VNF is instantiated.
- **Function Type:** LDAP. The seller defines the scope of its VNF.

```

{
  "id": "3341",
  "name": "VNF Offering with perpetual offer with flat recurring price",
  "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for OpenLDAP VNF",
  "version": "1.0",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2023-08-14T13:50:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2023-08-30T13:50:26.456Z"
  },
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "VNF Category",
      "description": "Virtualised Network Function category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [{
    "name": "Barcelona",
    "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona"
  }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "id": "legalProseTemplate",
      "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "name": "Legal Prose Template",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [
          {
            "id": "attachmentTemplate",
            "description": "Legal Prose Template for B2B purchases in a human legible format",
            "mimeType": "text/html",
            "content": "ZW5kb2JqCjQgMjYyYmoKPGMyAwAAWjJjCCADplsd44qWYYwqPj4KDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
            "size": {
              "amount": 1875,
              "units": "KB"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ],
  "prodSpecCharValueUse": [
    {
      "name": "License Model",
      "description": "Bought once, used for ever",
      "valueType": "string",
      "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "valueType": "string",
          "value": "Perpetual"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "State",
      "description": "Marketplace life cycle indication",
      "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "valueType": "string",
          "value": "Available"
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "serviceLevelAgreement": {
    "name": "basicSLA",
    "description": "Basic SLA for VNF/NS scenarios",
    "version": "1.0",
    "relatedParty":
  }
}

```

```

    {
      "role": "Seller",
      "name": "VSV"
    }
  ],
  "rule": [
    {
      "id": "availability",
      "metric": "http://IEEE99.5/Availability",
      "unit": "%",
      "referenceValue": "99.9",
      "operator": ".eq",
      "tolerance": "0.05"
    }
  ]
},
"productOfferingPrice": [
  {
    "name": "VNF Product Offering Price",
    "description": "Purchase cost (perpetual payment) plus recurring pricing (flat, fixed amount)",
    "version": "1.0",
    "price": {
      "unit": "EUR",
      "value": 120
    },
    "priceType": "Flat",
    "recurringChargePeriodType": "monthly",
    "recurringChargePeriodLength": 1,
    "prodSpecCharValueUse": [
      {
        "name": "recurring-payment-amount",
        "description": "This field defines the recurring amount to pay for using the VNF.",
        "valueType": "integer",
        "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
          {
            "valueType": "integer",
            "value": "50"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
]
},
],

"productSpecification": {
  "name": "VNF spec",
  "description": "Product Specification offering media services",
  "resourceSpecification": [
    {
      "name": "VNF Artifact",
      "description": "Tar.gz artifact containing an OSM-compliant VNF descriptor",
      "attachment": [
        {
          "id": "artifactId",
          "description": "Digest of the entire package per file",
          "mimeType": "text/txt",
          "content": "wAAwAAjCCADp1sd44qwYYwqPj4KZW5kb2JqCjQgMCMCBVYmogMyAKPDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWyw",
          "size": {
            "amount": 1163,
            "units": "KB"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
},

```

```

    {
      "id": "licenseModel",
      "description": "This attachment references the license model applied",
      "mimeType": "application/pdf",
      "content": "bb2JqCjQgMCBvYmoKPDwgL2Jqb2JqCjQgMCBvYmoKPDwgLCjQgMCBvYmoKPDwgLgMyAwIFiGL01lyIDc5Ml0K",
      "size": {
        "amount": 2264,
        "units": "KB"
      }
    }
  ],
  "resourceSpecCharacteristic": [
    {
      "name": "vCPU Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "value": {
            "name": "min-vCPU",
            "value": "15"
          }
        },
        {
          "value": {
            "name": "max-vCPU",
            "value": "15"
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
          "value": {
            "name": "min-virtual-memory",
            "value": "9728"
          }
        },
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
          "value": {
            "name": "max-virtual-memory",
            "value": "9728"
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "Storage Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
          "value": {
            "name": "min-storage",
            "value": "360"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "name": "max-storage",
        "value": "360"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "function type",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "LDAP"
      }
    }
  ]
}
],
"relatedParty": [
  {
    "role": "Seller",
    "name": "VSV"
  }
]
],
"lifecycleStatus": "Available"
}
}

```

Figure 4-1 - VNF Product Offering AIO

4.1.2 VNF Ordering AIO

Figure 4-2 shows an AIO document of a product order of a VNF. The Legal Prose already rendered to PDF is included as an attachment, and the *relatedParty* structure shows the two stakeholders involved in this transaction, the VSV that sold the offer of this VNF and the Vertical Service Provider (VSP) that has acted as its buyer through this order.


```

{
  "id": "2101",
  "name": "SC State related to OpenLDAP Order",
  "description": "SC State generated on instantiation",
  "version": "1.0",
  "state": "completed",
  "order": {
    "id": "2123",
    "description": "Product Order of the OpenLDAP VNF"
  },
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2023-08-14T13:57:24.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2023-08-16T13:57:51.296Z"
  },
  "place": [
    {
      "name": "Barcelona",
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "events": []
}

```

Figure 4-3 - VNF SC State AIO

4.2 B2C Scenario

This second scenario presents a situation in which a VSP wants to offer a form of access to a previously acquired VNF. The documents contain the DIDs of the other related AIOs.

4.2.1 NS Offering

This document, although it belongs to a different scenario, is still a product offer, so the asset provider must also include a way to remunerate it as was the case with the VNF offer seen in 4.1.1. This, for example, is used to define a way of earning revenue that is more beneficial for the NS seller than the VNF seller.

In this case, the NS license model is Perpetual type, with a price of 500 euros. The recurring payment, which occurs every three months, has a cost of 300 euros. Finally, to that amount, the PLA adds different amounts as charges based on the use of the NS, such as time of use or resources consumed.

All legal documents related to the network service that the VSP wants to create must also be included, as this service is a completely new offer even if it depends on an element which already existed in the Marketplace such as the VNF.

In Figure 4-4 it is possible to find an example of this type of document.

```

{
  "id": "8891",
  "name": "NS Offering with perpetual offer with flat recurring price",
  "description": "This JSON represents a productOffering of a NS",
  "version": "1.0",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2023-08-14T14:21.338Z",
    "endDateTime": "2023-08-30T14:22.116Z"
  },
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "NS Category",
      "description": "Network Service category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "name": "Barcelona",
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "id": "legalProseTemplate",
      "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the NS Offering in detail",
      "name": "Legal Prose Template",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [
          {
            "id": "attachmentTemplate",
            "description": "Legal Prose Template for B2C purchases in a human legible format",
            "mimeType": "text/markdown",
            "content": "sd44qwYYwqPj4KDs44qwYYwqPj4KDwgL1plsd44qwYYwqPj4KDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
            "size":
              {
                "amount": 1632,
                "units": "KB"
              }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ],
  "prodSpecCharValueUse": [
    {
      "name": "License Model",
      "description": "Bought once, used for ever",
      "valueType": "string",
      "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "valueType": "string",
          "value": "Perpetual"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "State",
      "description": "Marketplace life cycle indication",
      "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "valueType": "string",
          "value": "Available"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "Related Orders DIDs",
      "description": "References to previously placed Orders which need to be linked to this NS Offering",
      "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [

```

```

    {
      "valueType": "string",
      "value": "7611"
    }
  ]
},
"serviceLevelAgreement": {
  "name": "basicSLA",
  "description": "Basic SLA for VNF/NS scenarios",
  "version": "1.0",
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "role": "Seller",
      "name": "VSP"
    }
  ],
  "rule": [
    {
      "id": "availability",
      "metric": "http://IEEE99.5/Availability",
      "unit": "%",
      "referenceValue": "99.9",
      "operator": ".eq",
      "tolerance": "0.05"
    }
  ]
},
"productOfferingPrice": [
  {
    "name": "NS Product Offering Price",
    "description": "Purchase cost plus recurring pricing based on usage.",
    "version": "1.0",
    "price": {
      "unit": "EUR",
      "value": 500
    },
    "priceType": "pay-as-you-grow",
    "recurringChargePeriodType": "monthly",
    "recurringChargePeriodLength": 3,
    "pricingLogicAlgorithm": [
      {
        "name": "Pricing Script reference to Resource attachments",
        "description": "Algorithm to calculate the additional charges of the NS based on usage stats",
        "plaSpecId": "plaSpecIdInResource"
      }
    ],
    "prodSpecCharValueUse": [
      {
        "name": "recurring-payment-amount",
        "description": "This field defines the recurring amount to pay for using the NS.",
        "valueType": "integer",
        "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
          {
            "valueType": "integer",
            "value": "300"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
],
"productSpecification": {
  "name": "NS spec",
  "description": "Product Specification offering media services",

```

```

"resourceSpecification": [
{
  "name": "NS Artifact",
  "description": "Tar.gz artifact containing an OSM-compliant NS descriptor",
  "attachment": [
    {
      "id": "artifactId",
      "name": "Digest",
      "description": "Digest of the entire package per file",
      "attachmentType": "file",
      "mimeType": "text/txt",
      "content": "5kb2Jq5kb2JqCjQgMcbvYmwYwqPj4KzWokPDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
      "size":
      {
        "amount": 3301,
        "units": "KB"
      }
    },
    {
      "id": "plaSpecIdInResource",
      "name": "Pricing Script 1",
      "description": "Pricing script for time-of-use charging",
      "attachmentType": "file",
      "mimeType": "text/bash",
      "content": "yIDc5Ml0KPj4KzW5kb2JqCjQw5kb2JqCjQgMcbvYmoKPDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
      "size":
      {
        "amount": 1176,
        "units": "KB"
      }
    }
  ],
  {
    "id": "licenseModel",
    "name": "License Model",
    "description": "This attachment references the license model applied",
    "mimeType": "application/pdf",

```

```

    "content": "gyIDc5Ml0KPj4KzW5kb2JqCjQIFiGL01lgMcbvYmoKPDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
    "size": {
      "amount": 2098,
      "units": "KB"
    }
  }
],
"resourceSpecCharacteristic": [
{
  "name": "vCPU Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "name": "min-vCPU",
        "value": "15"
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "name": "max-vCPU",
        "value": "15"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "name": "min-virtual-memory",
        "value": "15168"
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

```

    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "name": "max-virtual-memory",
        "value": "86088"
      }
    }
  ],
},
{
  "name": "Storage Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "name": "min-storage",
        "value": "300"
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "name": "max-storage",
        "value": "5000"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "service type",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "LDAP Service"
      }
    }
  ]
}
],
},
"relatedParty": [
  {
    "role": "Seller",
    "name": "VSP"
  }
]
],
"lifecycleStatus": "Available"
}

```

Figure 4-4 - NS Product Offering AIO

4.2.2 NS Ordering

Figure 4-5 shows an AIO model of a product order of a NS. In this case, the *relatedParty* structure shows two different actors than in the B2B scenario. The VSP now acts as the seller of the network service, and it is the Vertical Service Consumer (VSC) who through this order becomes the buyer.

```

{
  "id": "7611",
  "name": "Product Order NS",
  "description": "This JSON represents a Product Order of a Network Service in a B2C scenario.",
  "version": "1.0",
  "orderDate": "2023-08-14T14:28.337Z",
  "completionDate": "2023-08-14T14:29.229Z",
  "state": "Completed",
  "productOrderItem": [
    {
      "quantity": 1,
      "action": "add",
      "productOffering": {
        "id": "8891"
      }
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "description": "Rendered Legal Prose describing the ordering in detail",
      "name": "Report PDF Document",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [{
          "name": "RenderedB2C",
          "description": "Legal Prose rendered with details of the ordering and buyer",
          "attachmentType": "file",
          "mimeType": "application/pdf",
          "content": "Pj4KZW5kPj4KZW5kb2JqCjQgMCRBb2JqCjQgMCRBwYYwqPj4KZVYmoKPDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
          "size": {
            "amount": 1147,
            "units": "KB"
          }
        }]
      }
    }
  ],
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "role": "Seller",
      "name": "VSP"
    },
    {
      "role": "Buyer",
      "name": "VSC"
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 4-5 - NS Product Order AIO

4.2.3 SC State

Finally, Figure 4-6 shows the SC State resulting from the B2C scenario use case.

```

{
  "id": "3668",
  "name": "SC State related to OpenLDAP Network Service Order",
  "description": "SC State generated on instantiation",
  "version": "1.0",
  "state": "completed",
  "order": {
    "id": "7611",
    "description": "Product Order of the LDAP NS"
  },
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2023-08-16T14:53:33.378Z",
    "endDateTime": "2023-08-16T14:54:11.256Z"
  },
  "place": [
    {
      "name": "Barcelona",
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "events": []
}

```

Figure 4-6 - NS SC State AIO

4.3 Considerations for Other Scenarios

The SC System will be able to handle offers focused on different types of assets. Specifically, these assets can reference a wide range of areas, which are VNF, NS, Edge, Cloud, Radio Access Network (RAN), Slice and Spectrum.

Since the areas to which an offer can adhere are very varied, it was necessary to have a robust data model that can adapt to all of them. For example, VNF, NS, Edge and Cloud offers have characteristics such as number of cores, amount of RAM or disk memory. On the other hand, a RAN service offer has operating bands, wireless technology or frequencies.

TM Forum models have enough flexibility to adapt to these different scenarios, since there are fields in which any characteristic can be inserted. For example, "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue" is a structure where is possible to define a name, a type of the value, and the value. In this way an enormous number of specific characteristics can be described.

An example of this structure adapted to two different scenarios is presented in Figure 4-7 and Figure 4-8. In the first case, it is defined the minimum amount of RAM that the NS requires. In the second case, it is depicted the isolation level of a slice type offer. As the structure has optional fields, such as "unitOfMeasure", the necessary ones can be applied depending on the case.

```
"resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
  {
    "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
    "value": {
      "name": "min-virtual-memory",
      "value": "15168"
    }
  }
],
```

Figure 4-7 - resourceSpecCharacteristicValue for Min Virtual Memory case.

```
"resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
  {
    "value": {
      "name": "Isolation-level",
      "value": "Physical Isolation"
    }
  }
]
```

Figure 4-8 - resourceSpecCharacteristicValue for Isolation Level case.

Table 4-1 shows all the specific fields for each type of asset.

Table 4-1 - Assets specific fields

Asset Type	Specific Fields
VNF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - vCPU (number of cores): min/max - Virtual Memory (MB): min/max - Storage (GB): min/max - Function Type
Network Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - vCPU (number of cores): min/max - Virtual Memory (MB): min/max - Storage (GB): min/max - Service Type
Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CPU (number of cores) - Memory (MB) - Storage (GB)
Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CPU (number of cores) - Memory (MB) - Storage (GB)

RAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RAN Type (Cell, Access point) - Technology (4G, 5G, Wifi5, Wifi6) - Operation Band - Central DL frequency - Central UL frequency - Bandwidth (MHz) - Tx Power (W) - Duplex Mode
Slice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Area of service - Max downlink throughput per slice - Max uplink throughput per slice - Isolation Level - Data Network Access - Access Technology - Radio Spectrum
Spectrum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology (4G, 5G) - Operation Band - Frequency Downlink (Start/End) - Frequency Uplink (Start/End) - Duplex Mode

The JSON Schema of the Product Offering AIO and Product Order AIO models are shown in annexes 7.2 and 7.3 respectively.

The final AIOs in our use case are documents in which fields that contained direct IDs to other TM Forum models have been modified. Although the schemas selected to represent the structure of the AIOs are aligned with the official TM Forum version, small modifications have been made when necessary, such as the elimination of many of those IDs since our documents are AIOs and the only IDs that are of interest to the document are the DIDs obtained by the DLT.

It is complex to find a single version of the TM Forum models and follow it in all cases, given that this organisation has released numerous versions of them in the last decade. In some cases, to represent a specific characteristic, a schema from a previous version does accept it, and the later version modifies something that makes it not possible to include that characteristic.

For this reason, and given that all versions are valid, the most recent one has been used whenever possible. In the case of the offer AIO, this version [\[17\]](#) has been used. On the other hand, this version [\[18\]](#) has been used for the Order AIO. Importantly, since schemas have many dependent subschemas, a previous version of a schema has only been used when strictly necessary, so AIOs maintain a consistent and up-to-date structure.

The AIO models schemas, which can be found in the mentioned annexes, will be included in the repository along with all their dependencies.

Finally, the JSON Schema of the SC State AIO model is shown in 7.4. This is the only AIO that is not built following any TM Forum specifications, as it is unique to the scope of the project but is inspired by their models to create the format of the fields and structures.

5 Conclusion

In this first prototype of the SC System, composed by the Dev Toolkit and SCSC components, a satisfactory point of results and integration has been reached. The functions of each element have been defined and delimited through adapted use cases, and its functionality has also been tested through tests defined for each situation. The future steps of each component have been explained in sections 2.6 and 3.6, and we hope to achieve them within the deadlines defined in collaboration with the other members of the project consortium.

The next global step in the development of the SC System will be defined in document E4.3 "Final Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation", where the improvements and modifications of the result of the workplan will be incorporated.

6 References

- [1] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023.
- [2] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023 – Section 4.3 “Low-Level Architecture”.
- [3] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023 – Section 4.4.1 “Dev Toolkit Commands”.
- [4] The Go Programming Language Specification v1.22 - <https://go.dev/ref/spec> - 06/02/2024
- [5] TM Forum site – Website, 2023 - <https://www.tmforum.org>
- [6] JSON Schema Specification – December 2020, <https://json-schema.org/specification>
- [7] Scaffold Template Generator Library for Golang - <https://github.com/metakeule/scaffold>
- [8] ChromeDP Go Package - Chrome DevTools Protocol for Golang - <https://pkg.go.dev/github.com/chromedp/chromedp>
- [9] Base 64 Encoding Specification - <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc4648#section-4>
- [10] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023 – Section 3.1 “Input Data Model”
- [11] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023 – Section 3.2 “Output Data Model”
- [12] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023 – Section 4.4.2 “North Bound Interface”.
- [13] Swagger: API Documentation & Design Tools for Teams – User Interface - <https://swagger.io/tools/swagger-ui/>
- [14] Swagger: API Documentation & Design Tools for Teams – Swagger - <https://swagger.io>
- [15] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 5.2: First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for SLA Assurance v1.0 – 31/01/2024 – Table 2.1 “Data Bus Topics”
- [16] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 2.1: Use Cases and Requirements Elicitation v1.0 – 31/05/2023

[17] GitHub TM Forum API Swagger - <https://github.com/tmforum/TMFAPISWAGGER>

[18] GitHub TM Forum APIs - Open API and Data Model - https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model

7 Annex

7.1 Swagger.yaml file with SCSC endpoints

```

info:
  contact:
    email: guillermo.gomezchavez@eviden.net
    name: Guillermo Gomez, Daniel Ruiz
    url: https://github.gsissc.myatos.net/GLB-BDS-ETSN-SECURITY/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/
  description: Entrypoint for stakeholder participating in the telco marketplace to onboard (offer and order), consult and deploy services
  license:
    name: Eviden (ATOS business) 2023
  termsOfService: http://swagger.io/terms/
  title: Smart Contract State Composer API
  version: "1.0"
paths:
  /discover/{intent}:
    get:
      consumes:
        - text/plain
      description: Obtain relevant ProductOfferings AIO published (by others)
      parameters:
        - description: Intent-based request
          in: path
          name: intent
          required: true
          type: string
      produces:
        - application/json
      responses:
        "200":
          description: OK
      summary: Marketplace offers available
      tags:
        - demand
  /health:
    get:
      description: Provides start checks for K8s
      produces:
        - text/plain
      responses:
        "200":
          description: OK
      summary: Health check of the service
      tags:
        - internal

```

```

/productOffering:
  get:
    consumes:
      - application/json
    description: Obtain all ProductOfferings AIO published (your own)
    produces:
      - application/json
    responses:
      "200":
        description: OK
    summary: All productsOffering owned
    tags:
      - supply
  post:
    consumes:
      - application/json
    description: Create a ProductOffering AIO published (your own)
    produces:
      - text/plain
    responses:
      "200":
        description: OK
    summary: Create a productsOffering
    tags:
      - supply
/productOffering/{did}:
  delete:
    consumes:
      - application/json
    description: Delete a ProductOffering AIO published (your own)
    parameters:
      - description: DID in the marketplace
        in: path
        name: did
        required: true
        type: string
    produces:
      - application/json
    responses:
      "200":
        description: OK
    summary: Delete a productsOffering
    tags:
      - supply

```

```

get:
  consumes:
  - application/json
  description: Obtain one ProductOffering AIO published (your own)
  parameters:
  - description: DID in the marketplace
    in: path
    name: did
    required: true
    type: string
  produces:
  - application/json
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: One productsOffering owned
  tags:
  - supply
put:
  consumes:
  - application/json
  description: Update a ProductOffering AIO published (your own)
  parameters:
  - description: DID in the marketplace
    in: path
    name: did
    required: true
    type: string
  produces:
  - application/json
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: Update a productsOffering
  tags:
  - supply
/productOrder:
get:
  consumes:
  - application/json
  description: Obtain all ProductOrders AIO published (your own)
  produces:
  - application/json

```

```

responses:
  "200":
    description: OK
summary: All productsOrder owned
tags:
- demand
post:
  consumes:
  - application/json
description: Create a ProductOrder AIO published (your own)
produces:
  - text/plain
responses:
  "200":
    description: OK
summary: Create a productsOrder
tags:
  - demand
/productOrder/{did}:
delete:
  consumes:
  - application/json
description: Delete a ProductOrder AIO published (your own)
parameters:
  - description: DID in the marketplace
    in: path
    name: did
    required: true
    type: string
produces:
  - application/json
responses:
  "200":
    description: OK
summary: Delete a productsOrder
tags:
  - demand
get:
  consumes:
  - application/json
description: Obtain one ProductOrder AIO published (your own)
parameters:
  - description: DID in the marketplace

```

```

    in: path
    name: did
    required: true
    type: string
  produces:
  - application/json
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: One productsOrder owned
  tags:
  - demand
put:
  consumes:
  - application/json
  description: Update a ProductOrder AIO published (your own)
  parameters:
  - description: DID in the marketplace
    in: path
    name: did
    required: true
    type: string
  produces:
  - application/json
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: Update a productsOrder
  tags:
  - demand
/smartContractState:
get:
  consumes:
  - application/json
  description: Obtain all SmartContractStates AIO published (your own)
  produces:
  - application/json
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: All SCStates owned
  tags:
  - deployment

```

```
responses:  
  "200":  
    | description: OK  
summary: One SCStates owned  
tags:  
- deployment  
put:  
  consumes:  
  - application/json  
description: Update a SmartContractState AIO published (your own)  
parameters:  
- description: DID in the marketplace  
  in: path  
  name: did  
  required: true  
  type: string  
produces:  
- application/json  
responses:  
  "200":  
    | description: OK  
summary: Update a SCStates  
tags:  
- internal
```

```

post:
  consumes:
    - application/json
  description: Create a SmartContractState AIO published (your own)
  produces:
    - text/plain
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: Create a SCStates
  tags:
    - deployment
/smartContractState/{did}:
delete:
  consumes:
    - application/json
  description: Delete a SmartContractState AIO published (your own)
  parameters:
    - description: DID in the marketplace
      in: path
      name: did
      required: true
      type: string
  produces:
    - application/json
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: Delete a SCStates
  tags:
    - internal
get:
  consumes:
    - application/json
  description: Obtain one SmartContractState AIO published (your own)
  parameters:
    - description: DID in the marketplace
      in: path
      name: did
      required: true
      type: string
  produces:
    - application/json

```

```

/render:
get:
  description: Request the render of the Legal Prose Template
  produces:
    - application/pdf
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
  summary: Request the renderization of LPT as PDF file
  tags:
    - internal

```

swagger: "2.0"

```

tags:
- name: supply
- name: demand
- name: deployment
- name: internal

```

7.2 AIO Offer Schema

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "aio-offer.schema.json",
  "title": "Offer AIO",
  "type": "object",
  "description": "Represents a Product Offering",
  "properties": {
    "href": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Reference of the ProductOffering"
    },
    "name": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Name of the productOffering"
    },
    "description": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Description of the productOffering"
    },
    "isBundle": {
      "type": "boolean",
      "description": "isBundle determines whether a productOffering represents a single productOffering"
    },
    "lastUpdate": {
      "type": "string",
      "format": "date-time",
      "description": "Date and time of the last update"
    },
    "lifecycleStatus": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Used to indicate the current lifecycle status"
    },
    "validFor": {
      "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/TimePeriod.schema.json#/definitions/TimePeriod",
      "description": "The period for which the productOffering is valid"
    },
    "version": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "ProductOffering version"
    },
    "@type": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Class type of the product offering"
    }
  }
}
```

```

"@baseType": {
  "type": "string",
  "description": "Immediate base (class) type of the product offering"
},
"@schemaLocation": {
  "type": "string",
  "description": "A link to the schema describing this product offering"
},
"place": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Place.schema.json#/definitions/Place"
  }
},
"serviceLevelAgreement": {
  "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/SLA.schema.json#/definitions/SLA"
},
"productSpecification": {
  "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/ProductSpecification.schema.json#/definitions/ProductSpecification"
},
"channel": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Channel.schema.json#/definitions/Channel"
  }
},
"serviceCandidate": {
  "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/ServiceCandidate.schema.json#/definitions/ServiceCandidate"
},
"attachment": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Attachment.schema.json#/definitions/Attachment"
  }
},
"category": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Category.schema.json#/definitions/Category"
  }
},
"resourceCandidate": {
  "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/ResourceCandidate.schema.json#/definitions/ResourceCandidate"
},
},

```

```

"productOfferingTerm": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/ProductOfferingTerm.schema.json#/definitions/ProductOfferingTerm"
  }
},
"marketSegment": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/MarketSegment.schema.json#/definitions/MarketSegment"
  }
},
"productOfferingPrice": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/ProductOfferingPrice.schema.json#/definitions/ProductOfferingPrice"
  }
},
"agreement": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Agreement.schema.json#/definitions/Agreement"
  }
},
"bundledProductOffering": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/BundledProductOffering.schema.json#/definitions/BundledProductOffering"
  }
},
"prodSpecCharValueUse": {
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/ProdSpecCharValueUse.schema.json#/definitions/ProdSpecCharValueUse"
  }
}
}
}

```

7.3 AIO Order Schema

```

{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "aio-order.schema.json",
  "title": "Order AIO",
  "definitions": {
    "OrderAIO": {
      "type": "object",
      "description": "Represents a Product Order",
      "properties": {
        "orderDate": {
          "type": "string",
          "format": "date-time",
          "description": "Date when the order was created"
        },
        "completionDate": {
          "type": "string",
          "format": "date-time",
          "description": "Date when the order was completed"
        },
        "state": {
          "$ref": "file://./tmforum-schemas/StateType.schema.json#StateType",
          "description": "Lifecycle status of the product order"
        },
        "productOrderItem": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "$ref": "file://./tmforum-schemas/ProductOrderItem.schema.json#ProductOrderItem"
          },
          "minItems": 1
        },
        "agreement": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "$ref": "file://./tmforum-schemas/Agreement.schema.json#Agreement"
          },
          "description": "A reference to an agreement defined in the context of the product order"
        }
      },
      "required": ["productOrderItem", "agreement"],
      "additionalProperties": false
    }
  }
}

```

7.4 SC State Schema

```

{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "aio-scstate.schema.json",
  "title": "SC State AIO",
  "definitions": {
    "SCStateAIO": {
      "type": "object",
      "description": "Represents a SC State AIO",
      "properties": {
        "state": {
          "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/StateType.schema.json#StateType",
          "description": "Tracks the lifecycle status of the product order."
        },
        "id": {
          "type": "string",
          "description": "DID field"
        },
        "validFor": {
          "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/TimePeriod.schema.json#TimePeriod",
          "description": "The period for which the productOffering is valid"
        },
        "place": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Place.schema.json#Place"
          }
        },
        "order": {
          "type": "string",
          "description": "DID of the related order."
        },
        "events": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "$ref": "file:///tmforum-schemas/Event.schema.json#Event"
          }
        }
      },
      "required": ["events", "order"],
      "additionalProperties": false
    }
  }
}

```

